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Case Study

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Understanding Informal Trading from the Public Perspective: The Case of Durban Central Business District

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Abstract

Evidently, street trading has become entrenched in our urban space, livelihood support for many, but also poses a challenge to the urban landscape. Hence, the aim of the paper was to assess the benefits and the challenges that characterise street trading, and how they have informed the management approach towards street trading in Durban. The research adopted a mixed research approach to accomplish the research objectives. The survey revealed that the challenges (59.47% of the respondents) posed by street trading were greater than the benefits (57.43% of the respondents) posed by street trading. However, of all the perception indicators, street traders as a source of employment received the most favourable response. Out of the 308 respondents, 306, representing 99.35% agreed to the idea that street trading provides employment.

Keywords: *Street trading, Inclusive management, Exclusive management*

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1. Introduction

Although sub-Saharan Africa, including South Africa, is the least urbanized region in the world, the rate at which urbanization and its challenges, notably higher unemployment, grow is alarming. According to Saghir and Santoro (2018), the current population of 472 million of urban dwellers is expected to double in the next 25 years makes the sub-Saharan the world's fastest urbanizing region. While other regions in the world, especially the developed countries are experiencing urbanization and economic growth concurrently, urbanization in Africa is taking place at a speedy rate with virtually no expansion in economic growth and no industries to absorb the unemployed who travel to the city (Bello-Schünemann *et al.*, 2016; Outlook, 2016; Jedwab and Vollrath, 2015). A situation which has led to the expansion in urban poverty and rising inequality (African Development Bank Group website, 2012). Hence, Tannerfeldt and Ljung (2012) contend that over 40% of city dwellers in developing countries, mostly the poverty-stricken, are compelled to turn to the informal economy as alternative measures of making a living despite the fact that the informal economy is widely regulated by outdated policies and laws.

Historically, in South Africa, despite being a livelihood support for the poor, street trading activities were not allowed in the cities under the apartheid government, since the cities were planned in accordance with a rational comprehensive

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planning approach which abhorred any form of informality including street trading. Hence, through legal policy and the use of brutal means, the informal economy was controlled and restricted by the apartheid government. People, mostly of black ancestry, who participated in any form of informal activities, were threatened by legal actions and police harassment. However, in the 1980s it became apparent that the apartheid government could not fully curtail the influx of black people who were mostly associated with informal trading activity into the urban areas due to increase in opposition to the apartheid government (South African History Online, 2019). By the early 1990s flexible approaches towards informal trading ensued in South Africa. Typical of such a liberal approach was the designation of the 1991 Business Act which allowed street traders to trade without any form of harassment (Budlender, 2003). Nevertheless, the lifting of the ban on street trading coupled with urbanization, mainly orchestrated by the demise of the apartheid regime, increased congestion in the major cities of South Africa, particularly the CBD including the Durban CBD. Street hawkers/traders wrestle with pedestrians and vehicles for control over limited spaces in the CBD turning the entire outdoor public spaces, particularly sidewalks and roadbeds into battlefields.

Although informal trading has continued to gain ascendancy due to the collapse of the apartheid regime, in recent times a high unemployment rate has also contributed to a surge in street trading in South Africa. According to Horn (2011), since 2000, the unemployment rate in South Africa has been between 24% and 30%. In South Africa, like most countries in Africa, expansion in the economy has not yielded to growth and redistribution of wealth. Consequently, many South Africans who are unable to find jobs in the formal sector fall in the informal sector as an alternative way of generating income.

According to Ofori (2007), street hawkers in their quest for spaces in the CBD, the focal point of commercial activities to display their goods, often occupy unauthorized public spaces, particularly pedestrian walkways. Encroachment on the sidewalk originally designated for pedestrian use impacts negatively on pedestrian and vehicular traffic flow. In support, Amoako *et al.* (2013) posit that such encroachment often impacts negatively on pedestrian movements with a ripple effect on vehicular traffic flow, since pedestrians are mostly forced to use the carriageway instead of the sidewalks. Also, Tulu *et al.* (2013) underpin the view that contestation for space between street hawkers on sidewalks constrains pedestrian and vehicular movement as pedestrians' resort to the use of roadways when the sidewalks are inundated with street hawkers and goods on the display.

Similarly, research conducted in Bandung-Indonesia, supports the notion that unauthorized occupation of street hawkers on sidewalks forces pedestrians onto the road which consequently impedes traffic flow as the number of road lanes are reduced leading to 'unidirectional traffic' (Chiu *et al.*, 2012). Additionally, Broadbent (2012) asserts that traffic congestion is directly linked to the presence of street hawkers since their activities cause drivers to drive at a slow pace to enable their passengers to purchase from hawkers or to avoid knocking over hawkers and/or pedestrians. Horn (2018) argues that in many countries regulating street trading, particularly mobile vending in traffic has become a challenge to most city authorities as prolonged periods of vehicular traffic congestions serve as fertile grounds for mobile hawkers.

Also, Selwyn (2018) argues that a surge in informal trading space along formal businesses embodies appropriation of undesignated spaces into trading areas. Eventually, such activities have reduced vehicular traffic lanes as pedestrians negotiate for space, mainly the carriageway, which has not been taken by unpermitted vending activities. As such, in the Durban CBD, at the Warwick Junction, a number of unpermitted street vending facilities are seen at the Warwick Junction, which have impacted negatively on the pedestrian environment, as sidewalks continue to be used for trading purposes.

Evidently, street trading has become entrenched in our urban space, livelihood support for many, but also poses a challenge to the urban landscape. Hence, the research aims at assessing the benefits and the challenges characterize with street trading that have often led to a debate, either in favor or against it; and ultimately the management approach towards street trading.

2. Informal Trading Management Approach

Management approach towards street trading may come in two main forms, inclusionary and exclusionary management often determined by the strength of the benefits associated with street trading or challenges posed by street trading. Most countries often resort to an exclusionary approach in dealing with street trading by removing them from public space, and in less severe cases, some or all vendors are relocated to a different place outside the corridors of the CBD, mostly to a secluded location with low pedestrian count or inadequate trading facilities (Roever and Skinner, 2016). To attain orderly conduct, state officials often aided and abetted by the law, resort to harassment and violent eviction (Recio *et al.*, 2017). A substantial number of cases relating to eviction of street traders in cities occurs largely in the global south. The situation is often intensified in the advent of major events or a function. Citing major events such as

the Federation International de Football World Cup and the Delhi Commonwealth Games where hawkers were driven out of the street prior to the tournament as examples, Skinner (2009) observes that major events play a critical role in street hawking eviction exercise. Similarly, in Ghana street hawkers plying their trades, particularly in the host cities were removed ahead of the Confederation of African Nations games 2008 (Moro, 2009).

In South Africa, during the World Cup 2010, as part of the agreement between FIFA and the host cities, wide exclusion zones around both the stadia and the ‘fan parks’ were created. Such exclusionary practices prevented street traders from using their usual trading sites to the advantage of the official sponsors of the world cup (Ivester, 2015). Similarly, in order to show readiness for the president of the United States, Barack Obama, on his assumption to the office of the presidency and his maiden visit to Africa all illegal trading stalls in Accra were demolished. In a like manner, the first visit of Pope Benedict XIV to the Ivory Coast led to the demolition of unauthorized stalls, particularly along the principal streets of Yaoundé to enhance the image of the city (Lewis, 2009). In 2004, the Durban municipal council approved the Public Realm Management Project with the objective of putting a stop to “illegal unlicensed street trading” as they were believed to be competing with formalized retail businesses. To make this a reality, an amount of ZAR 3.7 million budget was allocated to recruit 50 Metro Police Officers to execute the project (Xulu, 2015).

Approach	Explanation
Policy and legal provisions	Policies and By-laws are formulated and enacted to legitimize and recognize street trading activities.
Development of trading market	Creation of off-street markets for traders to ply their trade. Trading organizations are mostly involved during the creation of such a market.
On-site trading space upgrade and open-end design	This includes infrastructural upgrading and demarcation of spaces already occupied by street traders.
Permit/license provision	Trading permits/licenses are issued by the city authorities to legitimize the activity of street traders.
Flexible and mixed zoning ordinance	Space preservation along busy streets, commercial districts (malls), transport nodes and high-density areas are inclusively designed to accommodate street vendors under applicable zoning rights.
Privately managed permitted vending zones	Public spaces where street vendors are located are leased to private companies to manage on behalf of the government. In some situations, private companies go into development and renting of trading spaces to street traders.

On the other hand, it is acknowledged that street trading is difficult to regulate and manage in that movement of street traders is determined by events such as the weather, customers’ location, and the time of the day. Also, the fluid nature of street trading poses management challenges since most people trade for a short period of time in response to a specific crisis or transition (personal, family, job, in training, looking for another job), where street trading becomes a safety net. Therefore, street trading may increase or decrease depending on the times of economic crisis, rising unemployment, and economic growth. Again, to rectify the challenge of street trading by creating off-street markets, for example, may not be ideal since buyers will not follow the traders as new vendors invade the spots previously occupied by the displaced vendors (Dimas, 2008). Despite these challenges, there are interesting case studies, showcasing street trading management innovations, progressive implementation ranging from integrated approaches to support the issuance of trading permits, and infrastructural support, addressing the expulsion of street vendors and development of policies and laws in some countries. For instance, in Bhubaneswar, a city in Orissa, India, street vendors and pedestrian friendliness are encouraged as one-third of the sidewalk space has been specifically demarcated for their use while two-thirds are reserved for pedestrian use. Also, in Delhi, street vendors are integrated into a Bus Rapid Transit Pilot Corridor. Through the assistance of the Delhi Government’s Unified Traffic and Transportation Infrastructure Centre, a design guideline was introduced to include ‘Hawkers’ Zones’ in pavement design (Mahadevia and Vyas, 2012).

Similarly, in Bogotá, Colombia, the Supreme Court insists on the need to reconcile conflicting rights to public space, and also to find alternative means to eviction of street traders as embedded in the constitution. In view of this, an expulsion of street traders cannot be permitted unless it is ordered through an appropriate judicial process and assurance that traders will not be left to their peril after an eviction (International Labour Office, s.a.). Additionally, in Malaysia, street vendors are recognized. In 1990, in a National Policy on hawkers, a comprehensive plan to curb the social and economic challenges relating to street vending provided financial support in a form of credit schemes. Again, the department of hawkers and petty traders, with the aim of seeing to the development, modernizing and management of the street vendors with the objective of creating a good environment for the local people and tourists in Kuala Lumpur was established in 1986 to regulate and control street vendors (Indira, 2014). Similarly, in 1995 the Warwick Avenue Coordinating Committee was set up, and a budget was assigned to mitigate the challenges and upgrade in that area. The development led to the Warwick Junction Urban Renewal Project (Kitchin and Ovens, 2008) to tackle the urban management and design challenges as well as to promote transport, informal trading and employment in the area (Dobson and Skinner, 2009).

Approach	Explanation
Relocation without consultation	Street traders are often removed from their trading space to other areas without prior notice. In some cases, such new areas are off-street locations with or without development. The effect of this exclusive management practice is that traders lose their clients and eventually their income.
Long procedure to obtain a permit	Long process is mostly involved in securing a trading permit. The majority of street traders have less time and education which makes it difficult to cope with the process.
High registration and rental fee	New developments to include street traders often lead to exclusion due to exorbitant fees charged and as such most traders are not able to meet such financial obligations.
The use of hostile and ambiguous laws and policies	Street trading policies and laws are too many, bulky and interlaced with legal jargon which require time and a certain level of academic intelligence to read and assimilate in the end, most street traders violate the laws as they fail to understand the content.
Forceful confiscation of merchandize	Authorities confiscate the trading goods on numerous occasions without stating the reason for the seizure and issuing a receipt to the subject trader.
The use of media and the public to demonize the activity of street trading activities.	Often times, the media and the public tend to espouse only on the negativities associated with street traders; and in the end, the street trading business is given a bad reputation and image.
The use of force eviction and criminalization	Street traders are mostly removed forcibly from the public domain without being provided with an alternative site.

3. Research Methodology

The objective of the study is to investigate the factors contributing to the street trading management approach/criterion adopted by Durban, whether inclusionary or exclusionary using the Bromley (cited by Naik, 2015) argument on street trading. Bromley’s global review of street vending details a useful summary of the major arguments, mostly used to substantiate or discount the proliferation of street vending. However, the significance of the variations in argument is informed by the specific characteristics of street trading, trading goods and the area, city or country under analysis. Hence, each argument deserves careful empirical study within the context of its applicability (Naik, 2015).

To achieve these objectives, the study adopted mixed research approach. Primary data was secured through questionnaire and interview, while secondary data was secured through literature review. Moreover, the study secured information from 308 respondents, mainly road users (pedestrians and motorists), and experts using questionnaire. The selection of 300 road users and eight experts was to seek public view on the debate surrounding street trading, mainly in relation to the advantages and disadvantages of street trading which often determined the type of street trading management approach. While an inclusive management approach towards street trading was necessary, mainly due to some benefits associated with street trading, including provision of jobs, an exclusive management approach was often caused by the disadvantages, such as congestion, linked with street trading.

Strata	Respondents and Designation	Frequency
Road users	Pedestrians	150
	Motorists	150
Experts	eThekweni Municipality Officials: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • eThekweni Municipality Business Support Unit • eThekweni Informal Economy and Retail Markets • Market Management- eThekweni Municipality • Traffic Engineering-eThekweni Transport Authority • Road Safety Management-eThekweni Municipality • Personnel from African Council for Hawkers and Informal Businesses (ACHIB)-eThekweni Branch, • eThekweni Municipality Informal Economy Forum (EMIEF) member 	8
Total		308

4. Overview of Durban's Informal Trading/Street Trading Management

The eThekweni Metropolitan Municipality is situated on the east coast of South Africa, in the Province of KwaZulu-Natal. The municipality covers an estimated landmass of 2300 sq. km; mostly characterized by steep and dissected topography (eThekweni Municipality Integrated Development Plan, 2015/2016:97). The area shares a border with the Ugu District to the south, the Ilembe district to the North, the uMgungundlovu to the east and the Indian Ocean to the west as indicated on the district map below (Figure 1).

Source: Google image (2019) updated by the Author

Figure 1: Location of eThekweni Municipality in Provincial Context

Street trading management approach in Durban is mostly touted as one of the best on the globe. Nonetheless, this feat was not achieved overnight as a series of developmental procedures preceded it. The significant role of the central government regarding the passage of the Business Act of 1991 made it possible for traders to secure licenses to carry on businesses. Also, the Business Act of 1993 made it possible for street traders to trade without a license or any form of harassment as well as the 1996 Constitution which dismantled the apartheid machinery, followed by development at a local level.

Street trading has always been part of the urban informal sector of the city of Durban. African traders used to travel to the city on a five-day pass to trade their goods (Nesvag, 2002). However, often driven by two main reasons – the “sanitation syndrome” and “economics of space control”, laws curtailing the use of space by street traders were enacted. The Native Affairs By-laws introduced in 1916 by the Durban Town Council elaborated precisely on the procedures for the registration of Natives, mainly people of African descent, who required job contracts and passes in order to gain access to the CBD (Naidoo, 1993).

Moreover, the Durban City Street Trading By-law of 1962 (section J6) defined street trading as an illegal activity which made street traders culpable of an offence, and thereby spatially criminalizing street trading activities from taking Places in the CBD by restricting them to the peripheral zones, along main transport routes and outside demarcated zones (Do Rego, 1995). In addition, the Natal Ordinance 11/1973 introduced further curtailment on the freedom of street traders as it prevented street trading from occurring within 100 meters of formal business. Hawkers were prohibited from mounting fixed stands as they were not permitted to occupy a spot for more than fifteen minutes. Hawkers were compelled to move at least 25 meters away after every fifteen minutes (Nesvag, 2002).

In the 1980s, similar to any city in South Africa, the struggle for space in the city and the right to trade gained momentum when the apartheid machinery started to crumble, yielding to the relaxation of influx control (Grest, 2002). Coupled with the falling of the apartheid government and increasing mass protests by street traders, regulating street trading, particularly at the Warwick Junction, became expensive at the time. Hence, a new approach to deal with the informal sector economy became necessary. This led to the launch of two studies: the ‘Market Survey’ in 1983 and the ‘Hawker Report’ in 1984, into street trading in Durban. The research into the street market system, its extent, location and policy options for its management marked the defining moment of formulating a formal street trading policy in Durban, and other South African cities (Nesvag, 2000).

The reports argued for a reevaluation of the illegal status of street trading. The research made recommendations and introduced favorable policies to augment street trading activities. Popular amongst the recommendations, found in the Hawker’s Report of 1984, was the introduction of ‘immune zones’ designed in areas where traders currently traded, mainly in the CBD (Do Rego, 1995). The Hawker’s Report also proposed a more lenient approach to regulating street trading. It recommended a simpler licensing procedure. Again, the report recognized a certain degree of street trading management control to the success of street trading. Meanwhile, the Market Report of 1983 recognized market areas and transportation hubs as vital trading nodes due to the ability of such areas to attract high number of pedestrians. In 1985, a sub-committee was launched to find pragmatic means of formulating and executing friendlier policies and laws towards street trading (Nesvag, 2000).

The recommendations yielded results on the urban space of Durban as the number of street traders soared. The increasing number of street traders caused a form of chaos to prevail in the streets of Durban between 1991 and 1993, and led to the promulgation of a new By-law known as By-law M.N. 97/95. Section J.6 of the new By-law emphasized on ensuring appropriate sanitation at places of work and protection of public health. More so, the law emphasized on the display, removal and impoundment of trading goods. Again, general offences and penalties were also specified in the new By-law (Nesvag, 2002).

However, the new By-law was fiercely contested mostly by street traders and other pro-street trading organizations on the basis that consultation was not made when drafting the new By-law. Again, the traders disputed the laws criminalizing street traders. In addition, they challenged the By-laws by arguing that assigning full cleaning responsibilities to street traders contributed to a shift of public responsibility. In spite of these objections, the city officials went ahead to enforce ‘clean up operations’ to remove street traders who were deemed to be unlawful (Tsoeu, 2003).

From a departmental perspective, previously, the responsibility of managing street trading in South Africa rested on the Traffic Department. However, with time, this responsibility shifted to other departments depending on the city. In Durban, the Department of Informal Trade and Small Business Opportunities (DITSBO) now (ITSBO) established in 1991 is charged with the administration of all activities in connection with street trading. The ITSBO has an Informal Trade division which manages existing markets and establishes satellite markets. Again, the division has area managers,

and site supervisors who perform area-based work as well as providing training and support to small business operators. Meanwhile, the Small Business Opportunities division is responsible for policy and strategic development ([The eThekweni Municipal Informal Economy Policy, 2001](#)).

Through the work of DITSBO, new street trading By-laws were enacted in September 1995, and came into operation in January 1996. Moreover, from 1999 to 2000, the Durban city authority was involved in the consultative process leading to the drafting of the Informal Economy Policy to guide the city in the management of the crisis in the sector, and to define the city’s approach towards informal trading. The policy acknowledged street trading as one of the most vital sectors of Durban’s political economy. By providing jobs and ultimately income opportunities for thousands as well as making provision for goods and services mostly to a marginalized group at affordable rates, street trading has significantly impacted positively on the lives of the Durban poor, giving them a new meaning to life, space and culture in Durban ([Tsoeu, 2003](#)).

The first point of departure in the eThekweni Municipality Informal Economy Policy of 2021 is the mandatory role assigned to local government in promoting job creation opportunities under the Municipal System Act 32 of 2000. To accomplish this role, the local government encourages and promotes a diverse mix of markets and trading opportunities as part of the strategies to create diverse opportunities, and also to bridge the gap between informal and the formal sector of the economy. As a result, the eThekweni Municipality informal trading policy aims at planning and designing to accommodate informal trading in designated streets, public open spaces and markets in a positive well-managed environment. In view of this, the eThekweni Informal Economy Policy of 2021 argues for full integration of informal trading into the planning, design and management of the city to enhance city space, promote economic development and in turn expand job opportunities. Principled on sustainable urban management are four implementation levers or operational frameworks adopted in managing informal trading within the eThekweni Municipal Area (EMA) as illustrated in Table 4.

Table 4: Key Operational Framework of Informal Trading in the City of Durban	
Implementation Levers	Process
Planning	New markets and trading spaces should be planned in an appropriate manner, taking into consideration the economic needs of traders, the need for more vibrant land use, and the need for organized town, spatial and transport planning, as well as health and safety.
Allocation	The primary objective of the allocation policy is to support growth and provide economic opportunities for new entrants. As such allocating a site to new entrants for trading purposes has become one of the means of creating jobs and ensuring inclusion of formerly ostracized people.
Registration	The registration seeks to ensure that people working in public places are registered as small businesses. Registration and sustainable rental payments give permission to traders to operate, and also, to access services and support. As such, records compiled on traders may include the location of their trade and rent paying status.
Rental	Local governments consider informal trading as small-scale businesses, and as such value is placed on them in a form of rent. The rental value is determined by the place of location, size of the site, and the level of services associated with it.

The Business Support Unit (BSU) is charged with the mandate to manage informal trading in the eThekweni Municipal Area. The core functions regarding the management and development of informal economy, particularly informal trading and retail markets involve identifying management precincts; demarcation of trading area; issuing of permits; organizing traders into area committees that feed into citywide forum, and collection of rentals. Again, the management includes the implementation of laws governing informal trading and dispute resolution measures, particularly between residents, traders in the formal economy. These regulatory functions mandated by By-laws is achieved through the eThekweni Business Support Tourism and Markets Unit’s (BSTMU’s) Regional Offices, which render services to their clients, mainly informal traders with permits within their locality. The permit is an electronic system, where traders are issued with credit card permit type which allows the traders to trade in the sites allocated to them ([eThekweni Municipality, 2017](#)).

As part of the management of informal trading in the eThekweni Municipal Area, the Business Support Unit renders support to traders. The support may include goods display and exhibition, food handling and hygiene, waste management,

knowledge on By-laws and co-operative development, financial literacy, drafting of business plans, food handling, access to finance and agricultural development. These support and training which could come from internal or external source, are aimed at equipping traders with information and skills to run and grow their businesses in a profitable manner (eThekweni Municipality, 2017).

Table 5: Summary of Legal and Policy Documents Regulating Informal Trading in the eThekweni Municipality
Policies and Legislations and Their Impact on Street Trading
eThekweni Municipality Informal Economy Policy, December 2001: This policy serves as a guide that local authorities were to use in interpreting and applying By-laws and in economic development regarding the informal economy.
eThekweni Municipality: Informal Trading By-Law, 2014: This By-law spells out the specific details of the rules for informal trade in Durban.
eThekweni Municipality: Informal Trading Amendment By-Law, 2017: This By-law amended some provisions in the eThekweni Municipality Informal Trading By-law of 2014.
Informal trading rental policy/document: The policy deals with rental structures, determining rental values, the methods of rental collection and issues surrounding the non-payment of rents.
eThekweni Retail Market Policy: This policy mandate of the policy was to contribute to achieving the municipal constitutional mandate on local economic development. Also, to ensure continued existence of markets under the management of the city authority.
eThekweni Retail Market By-Law of 2014: This By-law was promulgated to regulate and control markets under the ownership and control of the municipality.
eThekweni Municipality Container Policy of 2006: The container policy sought to promote and develop container trading by making provision for mechanisms and tools to manage it.
eThekweni Municipality Itinerant Policy: This policy identified the research gaps that could improve the management of itinerant traders.
Street Trading By-Law: The law deals with prohibitions, restrictions, cleanliness of place of business and protection of public health, trading in parks and gardens, objections used for display of goods, and general offences and penalties.
Allocations Policy Governing Trading: The policy aims at providing growth support and opportunities for new entrants based on economic, sustainable, and social principles.
Source: Author’s construction (2019) adopted from multiple source

5. Questionnaire, Interview Results, Analysis and Interpretation

This section deals with presentation of questionnaire results by analyzing and interpreting the quantitative data that assisted in accomplishing the objectives of the research. The study secured information, mainly from group of respondents including pedestrians, motorists and experts to ascertain societal perception on the advantages and disadvantages of street trading.

From Table 8, of all the perception indicators on advantages of street trading, street trading as a source of employment received the most favorable response (306 respondents, representing 99.35%), followed by street trading as a contributor to the general level of economic activity through the sale of goods and service provision (232 respondents, representing 75.32%); and lastly, people’s perception on street trading bringing life to dull streets received the less favorable response (96 respondents, representing 31.17%).

Meanwhile, of all the perception indicators on the disadvantages of street trading as a generator of pedestrian congestion received the most favorable response (296 respondents, representing 96.10%), followed by street trading blocking the right of way of some places and buildings (240 respondents, representing 77.92), and street trading as a contributor to littering, mostly in their trading vicinity (216 respondents, representing 70.13%). Respondents’ perception

Table 6: Matrix of Descriptive Statistics of Related Themes Considered for Measuring Public Perception on the Advantages and Disadvantage of Street Trading (Numerical Terms)

Indicator		Responses										
		Road Users					Road Users					
		1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	
		Freq	Freq	Freq	Freq	Freq	Freq	Freq	Freq	Freq	Freq	
Advantages of street trading	1	Street vending serves as source of employment to many people	0	2	0	82	216	0	0	0	2	6
	2	Concentration of street vendors attracts potential purchasers into an area which ultimately leads to an increase in sales in other businesses in the area	26	78	39	145	12	1	3	2	2	0
	3	Street vendors contribute to the general level of economic activity through the sale of goods and service provision	18	46	9	142	85	0	1	2	4	1
	4	Street traders contribute to government tax revenue	21	73	57	63	86	1	2	1	4	0
	5	Street trading provides a safety net for the marginalized group	18	105	54	89	34	1	1	2	4	0
	6	Street vending provides a platform for entrepreneurial development	27	81	38	128	26	1	1	2	3	1
	7	Street traders assist in distribution of goods and services to remote areas and other areas where there are no large, merchandised shops	23	52	47	116	62	0	1	1	2	4
	8	Street vendors bring life to dull streets	67	123	16	62	32	1	3	2	2	0
		Total	200	560	260	827	553	5	12	12	23	12
Disadvantages of street trading	1	Concentration of street vendors in areas with a high successful business rate contributes to vehicular congestion	27	56	32	98	87	0	2	1	4	1
	2	Concentration of street vendors in areas with a high successful business rate contributes to pedestrian congestion	2	6	4	97	191	0	0	0	3	5
	3	Street trading contributes to pedestrian crash	37	78	36	117	32	0	2	2	3	1
	4	Street vendors sometimes impede the flow of emergency service vehicles as they may create access problems for emergency vehicles and service points such as water hydrants	58	78	69	72	23	1	2	1	4	0
	5	Street vendors may block the right of way of some places and buildings which may increase the level of tragedy in the case of an eventuality such as a fire outbreak or gas explosion	15	21	29	148	87	0	2	1	4	1
	6	Street traders compete with registered formalized businesses for limited customers	13	71	57	86	73	0	3	1	4	0
	7	Street vendors may cause school dropout as children of school going age often participate in street trading activities	61	76	19	97	47	1	1	2	4	0
	8	Concentration of street vendors in a limited space provides grounds for petty crimes such as pick-pocketing and snatch thefts to thrive	19	47	44	106	84	1	1	0	5	1
	9	Street vendors may cause noise pollution in the process of shouting to announce their products	22	93	18	126	41	1	2	0	5	0
	10	Street traders are involved in the sale of counterfeit and illegal goods	13	97	54	109	27	1	1	0	5	1
	11	Street traders may cause littering where they ply their trade	23	36	32	106	103	0	1	0	7	0
	Total	290	659	394	1 162	795	5	17	8	48	10	

Note: [1] Strongly disagree; [2] Disagree; [3] Neutral; [4] Agree; [5] Strongly agree.

Table 7: Matrix of Descriptive Statistics of Related Themes Considered for Measuring Public Perception on the Advantages and Disadvantage of Street Trading (Percentage Terms)												
Indicator		Responses										
		Road Users					Road Users					
		1	2	3	4	5	1	2	3	4	5	
		%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	%	
Advantages of street trading	1	Street vending serves as a source of employment to many people	0	0.67	0	27.33	72	0	0	0	25	75
	2	Concentration of street vendors attracts potential purchasers into an area which ultimately leads to an increase in sales in other businesses in the area	8.67	26	13	48.33	4	12.5	37.5	25	25	0
	3	Street vendors contribute to the general level of economic activity through the sale of goods and service provision	6	15.33	3	47.33	28.33	0	12.5	25	50	12.5
	4	Street traders contribute to government tax revenue	7	24.33	19	21	28.67	12.5	25	12.5	50	0
	5	Street trading provides a safety-net for the marginalized group	6	35	18	29.67	11.33	12.5	12.5	25	50	0
	6	Street vending provides a platform for entrepreneurial development	9	27	12.67	42.67	8.67	12.5	12.5	25	37.5	12.5
	7	Street traders assist in distribution of goods and services to remote areas and other areas where there are no large, merchandised shops	7.67	17.33	15.67	38.67	20.67	0	12.5	12.5	25	50
	8	Street vendors bring life to dull streets	22.33	41	5.33	20.67	10.67	12.5	37.5	25	25	0
Disadvantages of street trading	1	Concentration of street vendors in areas with a high successful business rate contributes to vehicular congestion	9	18.67	10.67	32.67	29	0	25	12.5	50	12.5
	2	Concentration of street vendors in areas with a high successful business rate contributes to pedestrian congestion	0.67	2	1.33	32.33	63.67	0	0	0	37.5	62.5
	3	Street trading contributes to pedestrian crash	12.33	26	12	39	10.67	0	25	25	37.5	12.5
	4	Street vendors sometimes impede the flow of emergency service vehicles as they may create access problems for emergency vehicles and service points such as water hydrants	19.33	26	23	24	7.67	12.5	25	12.5	50	0
	5	Street vendors may block the right of way of some places and buildings which may increase the level of tragedy in the case of an eventuality such as a fire outbreak or gas explosion	5	7	9.67	49.33	29	0	25	12.5	50	12.5
	6	Street traders compete with registered formalized businesses for limited customers	4.33	23.67	19	28.67	24.33	0	37.5	12.5	50	0
	7	Street vendors may cause school dropout as children of school going age often participate in street trading activities	20.33	25.33	6.33	32.33	15.67	12.5	12.5	25	50	0
	8	Concentration of street vendors in a limited space provides grounds for petty crimes such as pick-pocketing and snatch thefts to thrive	6.33	15.67	14.67	35.33	28	12.5	12.5	0	62.5	12.5
	9	Street vendors may cause noise pollution in the process of shouting to announce their products	7.33	31	6	42	13.67	12.5	25	0	62.5	0
	10	Street traders are involved in the sale of counterfeit and illegal goods	4.33	32.33	18	36.33	9	12.5	12.5	0	62.5	12.5
	11	Street traders may cause littering where they ply their trade	7.67	12	10.67	35.33	34.33	0	12.5	0	87.5	0

Note: [1] Strongly disagree; [2] Disagree; [3] Neutral; [4] Agree; [5] Strongly agree.

Table 8: Matrix of Descriptive Statistics in Support of Public Perception on the Advantages and Disadvantage of Street Trading (Numerical Terms)

Indicator		Respondents in support of perception				
		Road Users		Experts		
		Freq	Freq.	Total	Freq. %	Rank
Advantages of street trading	Street vending serves as source of employment to many people	298	8	306	99.35	1
	Street vendors contribute to the general level of economic activity through the sale of goods and service provision	227	5	232	75.32	2
	Street traders assist in distribution of goods and services to remote areas and other areas where there are no large, merchandised shops	178	6	184	59.74	3
	Concentration of street vendors attracts potential purchasers into an area which ultimately leads to an increase in sales in other businesses in the area	157	2	159	51.62	4
	Street vending provides a platform for entrepreneurial development	154	4	158	51.30	5
	Street traders contribute to government tax revenue	149	4	153	49.68	6
	Street trading provides a safety net for the marginalized group	123	4	127	41.23	7
	Street vendors bring life to dull streets	94	2	96	31.17	8
				$\bar{x} = 57.43$		
Disadvantages of street trading	Concentration of street vendors in areas with a high successful business rate contributes to pedestrian congestion	294	8	302	96.10	1
	Street vendors may block the right of way of some places and buildings which may increase the level of tragedy in the case of an eventuality such as a fire outbreak or gas explosion	235	5	240	77.92	2
	Street traders may cause littering where they ply their trade	209	7	216	70.13	3
	Concentration of street vendors in a limited space provides grounds for petty crimes such as pick-pocketing and snatch thefts to thrive	190	6	196	63.64	4
	Concentration of street vendors in areas with a high successful business rate contributes to vehicular congestion	185	5	190	61.69	5
	Street vendors may cause noise pollution in the process of shouting to announce their products	167	5	172	55.84	6
	Street traders compete with registered formalized businesses for limited customers	159	4	163	52.92	7
	Street trading contributes to pedestrian crash	149	4	153	49.68	8
	Street vendors may cause school dropout as children of school going age often participate in street trading activities	144	4	148	48.05	9
	Street traders are involved in the sale of counterfeit and illegal goods	136	6	142	46.10	10
	Street vendors sometimes impede the flow of emergency service vehicles as they may create access problems for emergency vehicles and service points such as water hydrants	95	4	99	32.14	11
				$\bar{x} = 59.47$		

that street trading contributes to vehicular congestion featured fifth on the list (190 respondents, representing 61.69%). Meanwhile, street vendors sometimes impede the flow of emergency service vehicles received less favorable responses (99 respondents, representing 32.14%).

Also, on the question of the advantages associated with street trading, on average 57.43% of the respondents agreed with the notion that street trading was beneficial. Meanwhile, on the issue of disadvantages of street trading, the average score indicated that 59.47% of the respondents agreed to the disadvantages associated with street trading. The survey revealed that comparatively, the challenges (59.47% of the respondents) posed by street trading were greater than the benefits (57.43%) associated with it. However, of all the perception indicators, street traders as a source of employment received the most favorable response. Out of the 308 respondents, 306, representing 99.35% agreed to the idea that street trading provides employment.

6. Conclusion

There are overwhelming benefits as well the challenges characterizing street trading activities. Therefore, the challenge rests on city authorities to realize that efforts made to eliminate street trading had yielded poor results due to the high unemployment rate. As such, street trading will continue unabatedly as long as unemployment gains ascendancy. In light of this situation, in the short term, harnessing the benefits of street trading is imperative, while the search for a lasting solution to curb the high unemployment rate continues. Currently, the informal sector remains one of the largest generators of economic growth in South Africa as well as job creation; thus, coordinated strategy was needed to ensure its sustainability (eThekweni Municipality, 2017), to facilitate economic opportunities through the informal economy. Accordingly, Durban became the first city in South Africa with the most progressive policy on street trading (Kitchin and Ovens, 2008). The eThekweni Informal Economy Policy of 2001 recognizes the challenging role of local government in terms of pursuing economic development and pro-poor policies. The policy serves as a guide to local authorities to interpret and apply By-laws and in economic development regarding the informal economy. The management approach towards street trading in Durban is inclusionary approach, supported with legal, policy, spatial and institutional frameworks. Hence, infrastructural range, including vending facilities, storage and ablution facilities, as well as workshops to empower street traders are provided by the municipality towards the success of street trading. In essence, the management of street trading in the Durban CBD follows the indicators of inclusive management mechanism, including policy and legal provision; development of trading markets; on-site trading space upgrade and open-end design; permit/license provision, and flexible and mixed zoning ordinance are adopted, although cases of exclusive practices, particularly impoundment of merchandize from traders trading without permits, still need to be addressed.

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